

Schmidt Ocean Institute Post Expedition Report

Dynamics of Sinking Microplastics

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1 Overview

SOI Expedition ID	FKt230802
Vessel	R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>
Expedition Name	Dynamics of Sinking Microplastics
Expedition Dates	2023/08/02 - 2023/08/07
Departure Port	Balboa, Panama
Termination Port	Balboa, Panama
Ocean	North Pacific Ocean

Map of Expedition Location

Figure 1: Map of Expedition Location.

1.1 Expedition Overview

Ocean plastic pollution is a critical issue, with the most significant challenge being microplastics found throughout the water column, not the large debris floating on the surface. Microplastics, ranging from 5 mm in diameter to as small as 1 μm , form through the breakdown of larger plastics by sunlight, water, and wave action. Over 10 million tons of plastic waste is estimated to enter the Ocean annually. While scientists currently have a good overview of surface-level waste, recent studies suggest that the vast majority of plastic that's entered the Ocean since 1950 (as much as 99.8%) has sunk below the surface — and this descent is understudied. Additionally, understanding the scope and implications of marine microplastic pollution is an enormous puzzle, complicated by the typical challenges of studying the deep Ocean— it is difficult to access and requires expensive and sophisticated equipment and research time. However, the pathways of microplastics to the seafloor are a crucial and underexplored component of their global impact. Given the wide distribution of microplastics throughout the water column and their pervasiveness across the entire ocean, it is critical to conduct comprehensive research beyond the surface layers to fully understand the extent of this pollution.

Evidence suggests that microplastics are ubiquitous in the Ocean. While larger particles, easily visible to the human eye, are commonly seen on the Ocean's surface, much smaller particles are in the water column or accumulate in seafloor sediments. These tiny particles are often only seen when water samples or collected sediments are viewed using a microscope. There is a distinct disparity in the composition of floating microplastics compared to those in the sediment layer. These differences suggest that composition and particle size may influence how microplastics are transported to the deeper marine environment. Understanding how microplastics move in the marine environment is limited, primarily due to a scarcity of in situ measurements. The major obstacle to collecting such measurements of microplastics is an issue of scale — getting large enough water sample volumes and small enough filtration resolution.

1.2 Authorizations and Permitting

Permit Number	Permit Authority	Permit Focus
170-23	DAOPANAMA	Work in Panama (western Side) for R/V <i>Falkor (too)</i>

1.3 Expedition Timeline

The expedition commenced on August 2, 2024, departing from Balboa, Panama, and returned to Balboa, Panama, on August 7, 2023.

1.4 Expedition Objectives

The expedition's objectives were to establish foundational knowledge about the dynamics of microplastic movement in the Ocean. The main objective of this research expedition in the Gulf of Panama was to investigate the vertical distribution of microplastics along the water column and to explore the processes governing how these pollutants sink to the seafloor. More precisely,

the goal of the science team was to investigate the vertical distribution of microplastics in the water column, focusing on particles as small as $10\mu\text{m}$, comparable in size to a droplet of rain, and explore the processes that govern the sinking rate of microplastics to the seafloor. Additionally, this expedition aimed to compare two different approaches for collecting microplastics in the water column of the Ocean, one method using a new piece of technology called the Aalborg University Universal Filtering Object (AAU-UFO), which is capable of 300-, 10-, and even $1\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ while rapidly filtrating large water volumes ($>1\text{ m}^3/\text{hour}$), and another using an in situ sampler called the McLane pump. Conducting the research in the Gulf of Panama allowed the science team to collect samples in an understudied area of the Pacific Ocean, where nearly 6% of the global marine trade occurs.

2 Expedition Accomplishments

2.1 At-sea Accomplishments

2.1.1 Science

Microplastic Sampling and Distribution

Microplastic samples were collected off the coast of Panama, an important region for global marine trade and off the coast of the second-largest producer of plastic waste in Latin America. The sampling aimed to provide a comprehensive picture of the distribution of microplastics from the surface water to the deep sea, covering a transect from coastal waters to the open sea. Figure 2 illustrates the overall sampling strategy.

Figure 2: Overview of the sampling strategy. Credits: Aalborg University, YourCreativeNinja, Alvise Vianello and Laura Simon Sánchez.

The main achievements of the sampling are listed below:

- Conducted effective continuous sampling of microplastics down to 10 μm in sub-surface waters using the plastic-free pump from R/V *Falkor (too)* connected to the AAU-UFO. This sampling took place along the maritime corridor of the Gulf of Panama to explore the imprint of marine traffic on the microplastic polymer composition.
- Documented the occurrence and distribution of small microplastics ($< 300 \mu\text{m}$ — the length of a dust mite) along the water column, providing new insight into how these pollutants are transported to the seafloor.
- Successfully conducted a comparison study of two different sampling methodologies, one using R/V *Falkor (too)*'s CTD and rosette and a new technology, an AAU-UFO, and a large McLane pump, to identify the most effective and accurate technique for sampling microplastics in the Ocean.
- Conducted CTD profiling at stations to collect environmental data from the seafloor to the surface

In addition to sampling, 907 sq km of the seafloor was mapped.

2.2 Post expedition Activities and Accomplishments

2.2.1 Microplastic Extraction and Identification

All the samples collected during the expedition were shipped to Aalborg University, Denmark, where they were treated and analyzed in state-of-the-art facilities for microplastic analysis. All the material collected on the filters of the UFO systems and the McLane pump was resuspended in special glass containers and digested using a combination of chemical and biochemical processes to remove organic matter but preserve plastic particles (Gunaalan et al., 2023; Rist et al., 2020; Simon-Sánchez et al., 2022). The prepared samples were then analyzed with Infrared Microscopy (μFTIR) via chemical Imaging (FPA- μFTIR -Imaging), which is a high-resolution analytical method capable of detecting microplastics (and other materials) as small as 10 μm . The freeware software siMPle, developed by Aalborg University and Alfred Wegener Institute (Primpke et al., 2020), was used to analyze the collected infrared data and automatically identify and quantify all particles in the samples. Figure 3 displays the sample preparation and analysis workflow for microplastics the scientists followed at Aalborg University.

Figure 3: Microplastic analysis workflow from sample extraction to analysis via FPA- μ FTIR-Imaging and automated microplastic analysis via siMPle software. Credits: Aalborg University. Alvise Vianello and Laura Simon Sánchez.

In microplastic research, tracking potential contamination during sampling, laboratory analysis, and characterization is of utmost importance due to the pervasive presence of plastic in our surroundings. Additionally, the paint of research vessels has been identified as a potential source of cross-contamination (Leistenschneider et al., 2021). To address this, "air blanks" (glass jars containing particle-free water) were collected during sampling to measure potential airborne contamination. Also, small samples of the different paints from R/V *Falkor* (too) were collected and characterized using ATR-FTIR (Attenuated Total Reflection-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy) (Figure 4). The resulting spectra were then added to the spectra database library used in siMPle, for the identification and characterization of environmental microplastics.

Figure 4: Images of the paint samples from the R/V *Falkor* (Too) and their corresponding ATR-FTIR spectra.

2.2.2 New Discoveries

The novelty of this expedition lies in several aspects. First, the Pacific side of Panamanian waters has remained, until now, an under-investigated area. This cruise is the first to provide insights into the occurrence and distribution of small microplastics from the surface to deep waters. Additionally, the opportunity to conduct continuous sampling along the maritime corridor of the Panama Canal allowed the scientists to trace, for one of the first times, the imprint of this heavily trafficked route. The survey was conducted using state-of-the-art sampling equipment designed to capture even the smallest fractions of microplastics, placing this study at the forefront of microplastic research.

Highlights of the Scientific Findings:

Continuous sampling of sub-surface waters along the Panama Canal maritime corridor revealed the following:

- Coupling the AAU-UFO system with the ship's water intake system proved to be an optimal method for sampling small microplastics. This approach allowed for the coverage of larger areas while steaming, providing higher spatial resolution and maximizing research time. Additionally, since microplastics often exhibit a patchy distribution, covering larger areas helped reduce the sampling bias. This method shows high potential for integration into "ferry-box" monitoring systems.
- Microplastics were detected in all samples, with an average concentration of 240 MPs/m³ and reaching up to 653 MPs/m³ in some locations.
- Polyester microplastics, including both fibers and particles, were the most abundant across most samples. These are likely derived from textile fibers and packaging materials. Potential sources include atmospheric transport (from short to long range transport) and inadequate waste management, such as inefficient wastewater treatment systems in coastal areas.
- A significant presence of Epoxy-Phenoxy resin microplastics was observed, potentially linked to the intense maritime activities in the Panama Canal region. Epoxy resins pose a hazard to marine biodiversity due to their high polymer risk, originating from both the material's properties and the chemicals involved in their production.

The vertical distribution of microplastics from sub-surface to deep-sea waters revealed:

- Both methods tested during the cruise for sampling microplastics along the water column—the McLane Large Volume Pump and the *Falkor (too)* Rosette coupled with the AAU-UFO system—proved efficient in collecting small microplastics. The McLane pump allowed for the collection of larger volumes of water (e.g., 0.5–0.9 m³ during this cruise), whereas the Rosette was limited to a volume of 0.27 m³. The system developed by AAU to couple the Rosette to the UFO enabled rapid filtration of the total Rosette volume, taking less than 30 minutes. This efficiency allows for better management of ship time. Additionally, since most research vessels are equipped with a Rosette of Niskin bottles, this system facilitates standardized sampling of microplastics along the water column. Nevertheless, differences in concentrations and particle characteristics were observed between the two approaches.
- Microplastics were detected in all samples. Preliminary data indicate an average concentration of 40 MPs/m³ in sub-surface waters, 88 MPs/m³ in samples collected above the pycnocline, and 70 MPs/m³ below the pycnocline. The variability in concentrations increases with depth.

- The composition of microplastics showed high polymer diversity, with the presence of 24 different polymer types. Polyester, polyethylene, and polypropylene were the predominant materials. Consistent with global plastic production trends, the most common polymers identified correspond to those most extensively manufactured (Geyer et al., 2017).
- The polymer diversity of microplastics decreases with depth, whereas the size of microplastics also diminishes, with smaller particles found in deeper waters.
- Current analyses are integrating the environmental data collected during the cruise with microplastic concentrations and characteristics to describe the potential factors driving the export of these pollutants to the seafloor.

2.2.3 Software Utilized

Software for expedition planning and geographical analysis:

- [PERPLEX](#) - Alfred Wegener Institute
- [QGIS](#) - QGIS developing Team

Software for sampling equipment:

- [Large Volume Water Transfer System \(WTS-LV\)](#) - McLane Laboratories

Software for sample and environmental data analysis:

- Resolution Pro Software - [Agilent Technologies](#)
- [SiMPle software](#) - Aalborg University and Alfred Wegener Institute
- [Spectragryph](#) - Friedrich Menges
- [R and RStudio](#)

3 Data

Datasets acquired during this expedition and those derived from the analysis of collected data and samples as of this report's publication date.

Data Type	Curator	Completed
Vessel underway data (CTD, Mutlibeam sonar, etc.)	Rolling Deck to Repository	Yes
ADCP	University of Hawaii Data Acquisition System	Yes
Processed multibeam sonar	MGDS	Yes
Water Samples: Physico-chemical properties	EarthChem, SESAR	
In situ measurements of marine microplastics in sub-surface waters	Aalborg University	Yes
Microplastic Occurrence along a vertical gradient	Aalborg University	Yes

Table 1. List of all publicly available data.

4 Appendix

4.1 Science Party Information

Scientist	Institution
Laura Simon Sanchez	Aalborg University
Alvise Vianello	Aalborg University
Asbjørn Haaning Nielsen	Aalborg University
Jeanette Lykkemark	Aalborg University

Table 2. List of scientists and students aboard Falkor (too).

4.2 Conferences/Presentations/Posters

Vianello, A., Simon-Sánchez, L., Lewandoswka, M., Lykkemark, J., Nielsen, A.H, Gomiero, A., Vollertsen, J. Mapping Microplastic Distribution in Maritime Corridors: A Continuous Sampling Approach. Conference MICRO2024 Plastic Pollution from Macro to Nano, Lanzarote, Spain - 23-27th of September 2024

Simon-Sánchez, L., Vianello, A., Lewandoswka, M., Lykkemark, J., Nielsen, A.H, Grøsvik, B.E., Vollertsen, J. Beneath the Waves: Vertical and Horizontal Microplastic Distribution in the Gulf of Panama. Conference MICRO2024 Plastic Pollution from Macro to Nano, Lanzarote, Spain - 23-27th of September 2024

Simon-Sánchez, L., Vertical Dynamics of Microplastics: The Overlooked Role of the Water Column as Reservoir. North Atlantic Microplastic Center (NAMC) Annual Workshop, Bergen, Norway, November 2023.

4.3 Student Projects, Thesis, and Dissertations

Master's thesis:

Magdalena Lewandowska, June 2024, Spatial distribution of microplastics in the Gulf of Panama. Master of Science in Environmental Sciences, Aalborg University, Supervisors: Laura Simon-Sánchez, Jes Vollertsen

Mikkel Weitze Mylund, Expected Spring 2025, Mapping the global distribution of microplastics along the water column. Master's Water Environmental Engineering, Aalborg University, Supervisors: Laura Simon-Sánchez, Alvise Vianello.

Short Term Mobility - Early Career Researcher - Knowledge Transfer:

Ana Molina Rodriguez, March- June 2024, Applied Microplastic Sample Preparation and Detection in Water Column Samples Using Advanced Vibrational Spectroscopy. Visiting Undergraduate Student from Universidad Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain. Hosted at Aalborg University.

4.4 Cruise Records

- [Cruise Logs](#).

4.5 Community Outreach

The sampling approach and equipment developed for the cruise were shared through various educational programs focused on marine pollution and microplastics research. Specifically, they were integrated into the Master's programs (MSc) in Water and Environmental Engineering and MSc In Geography at Aalborg University during the course Marine Pollution, including Sampling Techniques at Sea – From the Air-Sea Interface to Deep Sediments. Additionally, the methods were presented during the [PhD course Microplastic Research – Analytical Methods for Microplastic Quantification - Online \(2024\)](#), held by Aalborg University. The course hosted participants from more than 20 countries.

5. References

- Geyer, R., Jambeck, J.R., Law, K.L., 2017. Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Sci Adv* 3. <https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIADV.1700782>
- Gunaalan, K., Almeda, R., Lorenz, C., Vianello, A., Iordachescu, L., Papacharalampos, K., Rohde Kiær, C.M., Vollertsen, J., Nielsen, T.G., 2023. Abundance and distribution of microplastics in surface waters of the Kattegat/ Skagerrak (Denmark). *Environmental Pollution* 318, 120853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2022.120853>
- Leistenschneider, C., Burkhardt-Holm, P., Mani, T., Primpke, S., Taubner, H., Gerdtts, G., 2021. Microplastics in the Weddell Sea (Antarctica): A Forensic Approach for Discrimination between Environmental and Vessel-Induced Microplastics. *Cite This: Environ. Sci. Technol* 55, 15900–15911. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c05207>
- Primpke, S., Cross, R.K., Mintenig, S.M., Simon, M., Vianello, A., Gerdtts, G., Vollertsen, J., 2020. Toward the Systematic Identification of Microplastics in the Environment: Evaluation of a New Independent Software Tool (siMPle) for Spectroscopic Analysis. *Appl Spectrosc* 74, 1127–1138. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0003702820917760>
- Rist, S., Vianello, A., Winding, M.H.S., Nielsen, T.G., Almeda, R., Torres, R.R., Vollertsen, J., 2020. Quantification of plankton-sized microplastics in a productive coastal Arctic marine ecosystem. *Environmental Pollution* 266, 115248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVPOL.2020.115248>
- Simon-Sánchez, L., Grelaud, M., Lorenz, C., Garcia-Orellana, J., Vianello, A., Liu, F., Vollertsen, J., Ziveri, P., 2022. Can a Sediment Core Reveal the Plastic Age? Microplastic Preservation in a Coastal Sedimentary Record. *Environ Sci Technol* 56, 16780–16788. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ACS.EST.2C04264>